

Decision on imposition of sanctions against criminal organizations and their members.

Due to fraud, conspiracy aimed to suppress and to eliminate competition by means of unlawful censorship, concealment of facts, misleading of the public, fakery, brainwashing, corruption, and other anticonstitutional activities that lead to unlawful monopolization and unjust enrichment of persons involved in named conspiracy, the criminal proceedings have been instituted against Fernando de Yarza López-Madrado, Stig Ørskov, Paul Verwilt and other members of the World Association of News Publishers.

In order to prevent further violation of the rule of law and to countervail against monopoly on truth, I prohibit the World Association of News Publishers and other organizations, listed in a compilation referred below, and seize their property; these prohibition and seizure are valid immediately and irrevocable.

Said legal measures result from the tortious acts and taken on the basis of the law of obligations as defined in the German Civil Code (Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch, BGB) and as justified and specified in decisions mentioned in a compilation in accordance with the Nuremberg principles and provisions of the Constitution of the community Rus' and Berliner Verfassung.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 24.08.2020.

Reference.

A compilation of prohibited organizations.

<http://constitution.fund/judgments/prohibition.pdf>